

HOW TO IMPROVE ENGLISH GRAMMAR WHILE READING: EASY EXERCISES

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Annotation: The article below is very helpful for every learner of English as it serves to improve reading

Key words: read the sentence, parts of speech, auxiliary verbs, useful for beginners

1. Identify all auxiliary verbs

This exercise will be useful for beginners and those who forget about auxiliary verbs in writing or speaking. Highlight them with a marker or write out sentences in a notebook. Understand why you need to use an auxiliary verb in a particular case. After a while, all cases when it is necessary to write auxiliary verbs will be automatically deposited in memory.

2. Parse the sentence

Read the sentence and determine which word will be the subject, which predicate, circumstance, etc. Also determine the parts of speech: which is a noun, verb, adjective, etc. Over time, you will learn to "feel" which part of speech belongs to this or that word, what function it performs in the sentence. Subsequently, you will be able to guess about the role of unfamiliar words.

3. Pay attention to the use of tenses

As you read, pay attention to the use of the tenses of the English language. Try to explain why a particular time is used in a sentence. If you are reading a newspaper, mark with a marker all the sentences where the time you are studying at this stage of training occurs. Also set aside time that you find difficult to use. When reading an article on the Internet or a regular book, we recommend that you write out such sentences or passages of phrases. After reading, try to retell the text using all the words written out. So you will consolidate in practice in which cases this or that time is used, and for colloquial speech such an exercise will be useful. To learn how to easily use all 12 tenses, take the video course "The System of the Times of the English Language".

4. Highlight the connecting words

As you read, pay attention to the connecting words (also, because, as ... as, although, however). Determine how they connect the two parts of the sentence, which word is used in a particular case.

5. Pay attention to punctuation marks

The punctuation rules of the English language are strikingly different from the Russian ones. Some students complain that memorizing them is difficult. Pay attention to how punctuation marks are placed in the text, after which words or in which sentences they are used.

6. Fill knowledge gaps

Identify your grammar spaces. To do this, you can use various tests, for example, on the ego4u.com or englishteststore.net resources. Work with the found spaces in the same way as in the previous paragraphs. Highlight similar moments in the text, try to make a couple of sentences with each of them. Bring the skill of using a particular design to automatism.

7. Use search engines

After completing the previous point, you already know your weak points. To work them out better, we suggest doing the following exercise. Let's say you don't understand the use of Present Perfect time. Write part of the phrase at this time on Google, for example, "I have read" or "I have seen" (for accuracy, use quotation marks). As a result, you will receive several hundred articles with a natural use of this time. Read small excerpts of several texts, pay attention with what words, in what cases Present Perfect is used. This is a living example of how English grammar works.

8. Read the news

Reading good classical literature is always helpful, but remember that the language is constantly changing. The most modern version of the English language can be seen in English-language newspapers and news. Hence the conclusion: if you want to learn how to build a sentence as a medium, read the news. The most interesting news without politics can be read at newsinlevels.com, the resource is suitable even for beginners. And for people with an average level of knowledge, we recommend starting to read the articles of the famous British newspaper The Times or the American edition of The Washington Post. Newspapers are good for three reasons:

The articles use modern language, the text is written correctly, the sentences are built in accordance with modern English rules.

Articles on various topics will help you not only hone your grammatical skills, but also increase your vocabulary and broaden your horizons.

Most of the texts are not too long, you just need to allocate about 30 minutes a day to work with the article.

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